

Chemical Nature of Lac Resin

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THE tiny insect, *Laccifer lacca* Kerr (Family : *Lacciferidae* Cockerell) elaborates a resin, known as lac. This material has been known in India since very ancient times, having been first described in Atharva Veda¹. Lac is a versatile resin and is of considerable commercial importance, especially to our country. India, which accounts for almost 70% of the total world production of lac², exported during 1971-1972, around 14,000 tonnes of lac, valued at ~ Rs. 6.5 crores³. Lac cultivation, being a source of subsidiary income to certain economically backward areas of the country, has considerable socio-economic importance. In view of this, a systematic study of the chemistry of lac resin was undertaken at the National Chemical Laboratory, Poona, as the information thus gained, was expected to have a direct bearing on the more sophisticated uses of lac. This article summarises the present state of knowledge of the chemistry of lac resin.

Introduction

As an introduction it would be appropriate to briefly describe the cultivation of lac, as well as summarise the background knowledge on the chemistry of lac, at the time the present investigations were undertaken (1962).

The life cycle of the lac insect⁴ starts as a tiny, crimson larva, which settles on a tender branch of a host tree, usually Palas (*Butea monosperma* Taub.), Kusum (*Schleichera oleosa* Oken) or Ber (*Zizyphus mauritiana*). Within a day or two of its settling, the larva starts secreting lac from almost all over its body. The lac layer slowly grows and under it the larva also grows and moults. After achieving sexual maturity (2-3 months), the males soon die, but the females continue to grow and secrete lac with greater vigour for several weeks. In course of time the female insect lays eggs, which hatch almost immediately into larva, to start a new generation. A female insect may produce 300-1000 larvae. The lac insect

normally completes two cycles in a year, thus giving two lac crops. It has been estimated⁵ that each healthy female produces some 30-70 mg of lac and thus one tonne of lac represents the work of approx. two crore insects !

In practice, lac cultivation involves cutting a small branch of the tree on which lac has been grown, at the time when the eggs are expected to hatch and, tying this twig on a new host tree which is bringing forth new shoots. In course of time (~ 6 months) the branches of the host tree get covered by a continuous encrustation. Raw lac, just collected by cutting and scraping of the twigs is called *sticklac*. This material, after partial purification by crushing, sieving, water-washing and sedimentation in water is known as *seedlac*. Further purification gives the *shellac* of commerce⁴.

Chemistry of lac has been studied on and off since the beginning of the nineteenth century. Stick lac can be grossly separated into wax (6-7%), coloring matter (4-8%) and resin (70-80%) fractions. Though, these fractions have been often investigated, there was much confusion in the literature at the time (1962), the present investigations were undertaken. Since then, a detailed study on the nature of lac wax has appeared⁶ and the structures of the coloring matters, erythrolaccin (I)⁷ and laccaic acids (e.g. II)⁸ have been elucidated. Lac resin has been known, for a long time, to be a polyester-based resin, derived from certain hydroxy acids and a number of these acids (lac acids) have been isolated by alkaline hydrolysis of lac.

However, structures of only two of these, viz. aleuritic acid (III)⁹ and shellolic acid (IV)¹⁰ had been established by 1962, when work on lac resin was undertaken in Poona. Our programme envisaged (i) elucidation of structures of remaining known lac acids and isolation and characterisation of any new ones, (ii) determination of the nature of 'hard' and

I

II

III

IV

'soft' resins as derived from lac. briefly summarise our findings.

Lac Acids

Alkaline hydrolysis of lac generates a complex mixture of acids. Literature¹¹ records a number of

The following pages

lac acids, however only butolic acid¹², besides aleuritic and shellolic acids had been consistently obtained and well-characterised. Butolic acid was identified as 6-hydroxy-tetradecanoic acid (V), independently and almost at the same time by Gunstone and co-workers¹³ and by us^{14,15}. An acid, m.p. 238°, had been isolated by Kirk and co-workers¹⁶ from lac hydrolysate and

V

VI : R = COOH

IX

VII : R = CHO

VIII : R = CH₂OH

X

XI : R = COOH

XII : R = CHO

was considered by these authors to be isomeric with shellolic acid ; this acid has now been identified as epishellolic acid (VI)^{15,17}. Another acid, jalaric acid had been isolated earlier¹⁸ in a grossly impure state. It has been possible now to get it in a pure crystalline state and establish¹⁹ its structure as VII.

In addition to the acids mentioned earlier and which had been described or noted by earlier investigators, we have succeeded in isolating five new lac acids from lac hydrolysate. These are laksholic acid (IX)¹⁵, epilaksholic acid (VIII)¹⁵, laccishellolic acid (X)²¹, epilaccishellolic acid (XI)²¹ and laccijalaric acid (XII)²¹. We consider that jalaric and laccijalaric acids are the primary terpenic lac acids and the other acids arise from these during base hydrolysis by equilibration (*via* epimerisation) at C₇ and Cannizzaro reaction. In support of this, it has been demonstrated¹⁵ that these aldehydic acids can be isolated only after a brief hydrolysis of lac by alkali and that pure jalaric acid on a prolonged exposure to aqueous sodium hydroxide generates shellolic (IV), epishellolic (VI), laksholic (IX) and epilaksholic acids (VIII).

It may be mentioned here that the cedrane skeleton for shellolic acid (and related compounds) is well-secured by sound degradative¹⁰ and X-ray evidence²⁰, whereas the structure of laccijalaric acid (and hence laccishellolic and epilaccishellolic acids) has been unequivocally established by a direct chemical correlation¹⁹ with (-) - α -cedrene.

To act as reference data, paper and thin-layer chromatography (TLC) characteristics of the various lac acids and their methyl esters, have been collected²¹. Methods were also worked out for the quantitative estimation of aleuritic and jalaric acids²¹.

Hard Resin

Lac resin is a complex blend of polyesters of different molecular sizes and has been separated into 'soft' and 'hard' resin fractions. For the present work we adopted a modified separation procedure²¹ for the preparation of 'hard' and soft' resins. Hard resin constitutes $\sim 70\%$ of the total lac resin, and is in itself a mixture of several polyesters. By solvent precipitation method, it has been possible to separate from *Palas* hard resin, an essentially pure lac resin fraction (termed, *pure lac resin*)²³. Though this material was obtained in a yield of $\sim 12\%$ (based on hard resin), its less pure form is obtainable in $\sim 50\%$ yield and thus, appears to be the major species constituting the hard resin. Consequently, to gain

insight into the nature of hard resin, further work was restricted to pure lac resin.

Constituent acids of pure lac resin²³

Saponification of pure lac resin by 12% aqueous potassium hydroxide for 5 hr at room temperature, furnished a hydrolysate containing aleuritic (III), jalaric (VII), laccijalaric (XII), shellolic (IV) and epishellolic acids (VI), as revealed by the paper chromatography of the resulting acids ; no butolic acid (V) was detected. This finding was fully supported by results of an extended hydrolysis ($\sim 30^\circ$, 10 days) of pure lac resin and identifying the products by paper chromatography and, after esterification, by TLC. Thus, it becomes clear that pure lac resin is derived from aleuritic, jalaric (shellolic, epishellolic) and laccijalaric acids.

Estimation of constituent acids of pure lac resin

This phase of the work has turned out to be quite complex and involved because of certain unexpected difficulties. Obviously the method of choice would be the gas-liquid-chromatography (GLC) of the methyl esters of the total acids obtainable on hydrolysis. However, for two reasons this method could not be adopted. Firstly, it was known from our earlier results¹⁵ that the reaction of jalaric acid and diazomethane is quite complex, resulting in a number of products. Secondly, attempted GLC of pure dimethyl shellolate/dimethyl epishellolate was accompanied by decomposition on a few columns investigated. Thus, it became obvious that at least some of the lac acids must be modified to get more volatile/stable products for GLC estimation (as Me esters). Two methods have now been worked out. The first method involves oxidation (chromic acid oxidation-esterification-GLC estimation), while the second makes use of formylation. These methods are briefly described below. However, there is an apparent contradiction in the results as obtained by these two methods. This as well as how the issue has been resolved, are also discussed below.

Chromic acid oxidation—esterification—GLC estimation²³.

It is reasonable to assume that the hydroxyl groups in shellolic/epishellolic acid could be responsible for transformation on GLC columns, and hence it was decided to oxidize these functions and then standardize their estimation in terms of GLC estimation of the major oxidation product. This necessitated a

study of oxidation of all the lac acids obtainable on hydrolysis of pure lac resin, in order to arrive at the most appropriate reaction conditions and obtain reference samples of the oxidation products. Chromic acid (Jones reagent) appeared to be the choice oxidizing agent as, this should convert jalaric (VII), epishelloic (VI) and epilaksholic acids (VIII) to the same (major) product, *viz.* the keto tricarboxylic acid (XIII), thus simplifying analysis, as of these three acids (VI, VII, VIII) only jalaric acid is considered to be the primary lac acid.

Using dimethyl epishellolate as the substrate, experimental parameters were standardised and, it was established that Jones oxidation of epishelloic acid, followed by esterification of the product with methanol-sulphuric acid, yielded a material (60% yield) shown by GLC to consist of XIV (84%) and XV (5%) and two other unidentified products. In the same manner, the product composition from jalaric acid (total yield 66%; 54% XIV, 11% XV, balance unidentified), laccijalaric acid (total yield 75%; 70% XIV, 20% XVII, 10% unidentified) and aleuritic acid (total yield 85%; 42% dimethyl pimelate and 49% dimethyl azelate, 9% unidentified) was ascertained.

XIII : R = H

XIV : R = Me

XV

XVI

XVII

The sequence, oxidation—esterification—GLC analysis, as standardised for individual lac acids, was next applied to the total lac acid mixture obtained after 48 hr alkaline hydrolysis of pure lac resin. In this way, it was found that for every mole of laccijalaric acid, approximately three moles of aleuritic

acid and five moles of jalaric/epishelloic acid are produced on hydrolysis of pure lac resin. It may be noted that in these calculations yields of various products were corrected in terms of actual yields obtained with pure acids and the unidentified products were ignored.

Alkaline silver oxide hydrolysis/oxidation—esterification—formylation—GLC estimation²⁵.

It has been found that GLC of lac acid esters can be conveniently carried out, without decomposition, after formylation and, an unknown mixture of pure derivatives can be quantitatively analyzed using an internal standard (ethyl triacetylaleuritate). However, it was soon realised that a synthetic mixture of pure lac acids (jalaric acid, aleuritic acid) on exposure to alkali (under conditions necessary for the hydrolysis of pure lac resin) followed by esterification (CH_2N_2) and formylation (acetic-formic anhydride) gave a material which on GLC eluted to the extent of only 50-60% (as compared with the standard) and the peaks no longer corresponded to the original ratios. This situation could be rectified when it was found that if exposure to alkali is done in presence of silver oxide and then the product esterified and for-

mylated, the resulting material, though still showing incomplete elution (70-75%) from a GLC column, fairly accurately gave component analysis. When this method was applied to pure lac resin, it was most surprisingly found that pure lac resin generates for every one mole of laccijalaric acid approximately

three moles of jalaric acid and four of aleuritic acid (cf. data disclosed above).

Conclusion

Of the two methods discussed above, the second is more straightforward and was tested on a number of synthetic mixtures. This method also gave the correct jalaric acid/aleuritic acid ratio for jalaric ester-II (XXI), a component of soft resin (*vide infra*). Thus, we conclude that in pure lac resin we have aleuritic acid and terpenic acids (jalaric/laccijalaric acid and the derived dicarboxylic acids) in a ratio of 1:1. This conclusion, however, conflicts with our previous finding²³ that pure lac resin on hydrolysis shows only 36±1% aleuritic acid by periodic acid estimation; this situation is reconciled by the fact that during hydrolysis of lac resin other side reactions occur and as a matter of fact, a 1:1 (molar) mixture of aleuritic acid and jalaric acid after being subjected to the conditions of alkaline hydrolysis, assays for no more than 40% aleuritic acid (periodic acid titration). The 1:1 molar ratio is fully borne out by a detailed NMR analysis of formylated pure lac resin.

Thus, it appears certain that each molecule of pure lac resin is derived from four terpenic (three jalaric/epishellolic acid and, one laccijalaric/epilaccishellolic acid) and four aleuritic acid units. Such a molecule should have molecular weight 2194 (considering only aldehyde functions at C₇) which is quite in accord with the value 2095±110 reported earlier²³.

Structure²⁵

Chromic acid (Jones reagent) oxidation of pure lac resin, followed by base hydrolysis and identification of products showed that the important points of linkage of the constituent acids are as shown in Fig. 1²⁴. It has now been possible to confirm and extend these findings by a detailed analysis of the NMR spectra of pure lac resin as such (in CD₃COOD) and after esterification (CH₂N₂) and formylation. The various signal assignments became possible after a study of the NMR spectra of soft resin constituents, described below. Structure shown in Fig. 2 appears most suitable. It is fully consistent with the NMR data and meets the major findings from chemical degradation²⁴.*

* This will be discussed in detail elsewhere.

Soft Resin²⁶

From the soft resin fraction of *Palas* seedlac it has been possible to isolate four essentially pure acid esters, which together constitute the bulk of the soft resin. These compounds have been shown to possess structures XVIII, XIX, XX and XXI and have been designated laccijalaric ester-I, jalaric ester-I; laccijalaric ester-II and jalaric ester-II respectively.

R = CHO/COOH

○ indicates group is free

□ → indicates group is linked

□ □ □ indicates group is free or linked

Fig. 1 Points of linkage of constituent acids of 'pure lac resin.'

Structures of jalaric ester-II (XXI) and laccijalaric ester-II (XX) were confirmed by partial synthesis.

R = CHO/COOH

R' = CH₂OH/CH₃ (On the average three out of four units have R' = CH₂OH)

Fig 2 Structure of 'pure lac resin'

XVIII : R = Me

XIX : R = CH₂OH

XX : R = Me

XXI : R = CH₂OH

Conclusion

From the present investigations it appears reasonable to suggest that the soft resin constituents (XX, XXI) may be the immediate building blocks of hard resin, in which molecular species containing four such units predominate ; it is very likely that species with three and five units are also present. Depending on the age of the sample and the care taken during its collection, significant oxidation of aldehyde function, apparently occurs. It is also reasonable to suppose that ageing of lac (storage, exposure to light, air, moisture) will result in, what may be called secondary structural changes. It is not necessary that the molecular species constituting 'pure lac resin' should be sequence-wise homogenous or even in terms of jalaric/laccijalaric acid ratio ; structures shown in Fig. 2 should represent the average situation.

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